

Prototype pre-Class Website Development as an Improvement of Java Language Learning in SMK

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Subject Area : Culture changes

Abstract

This study aims to produce a website as enrichment for Javanese learning material in vocational schools. This study uses the Research and Development (R&D) research method. The results of this study consisted of three discussions, namely the needs of teachers and students for material enrichment, enrichment of website prototypes, and the results of pre-class website prototype validation tests as enrichment of Javanese learning in vocational schools. Questionnaires for teacher and student needs were used to construct a prototype "pre-class" enrichment site. The developed prototype of the enrichment website is categorized into four main sections, namely homepage, about me, enrichment, digital library, and contacts. The homepage contains an introduction, developer profile, and buttons for enrichment pages and digital libraries. The about me section contains a website developer biography. The enrichment section contains enrichment material for Javanese learning materials for Javanese speech levels. The digital library section contains digital e-books as supporting material for learning Javanese. The contact section contains a form that can be used to contact the developer. Based on the assessment conducted by website and book experts, this website can attract students' interest to learn Javanese independently.

Keywords: – Enrichment, Website, Java Language Learning

Introduction/Background

The Governor of East Java Decree Number 19 of 2014 stipulates that the Javanese language curriculum must be implemented by all public and private schools (SMA / SMALB / SMK / MA) in East Java which has an impact, among others, the provision of teaching staff, preparation of facilities and infrastructure, and no less. the importance is the preparation of learning tools (which accompany the curriculum) and learning design.

Javanese language and literature as subjects have different characteristics from other subjects, for

example, mathematics, history, entrepreneurship, etc. In principle, Javanese language and literature are social facts as a means of communication. In other words, on the one hand, the Javanese language is a means of communication, and Javanese literature is a cultural product that uses language as its creative tool, while on the other hand Javanese language and literature must be taught to students through certain approaches in accordance with its essence and function. The language learning approach focuses more on the performance aspects of language performance and language functions, so the right approach to use is the communicative

approach. Meanwhile, the literature learning approach focuses more on the appreciation of literary works, so that the appropriate approach used is the appreciative approach.

Language learning is shown in the ability of students to use the language according to the context or is pragmatic. Therefore, pragmatic language communication is more of a form of performance than a scientific system. This view has the consequence that language learning should place more emphasis on the function of language as a means of communication rather than learning about linguistics.

Javanese is one of the regional languages in Indonesia. The language is still actively used as a means of daily communication between residents by the speaking community covering the DIY area in Central Java, East Java, and other areas where transmigrants from Java Island live. Due to the wide use of the Javanese language, regional features emerged in the release of the Javanese language called a dialect. In connection with the foregoing, the existence of the Javanese language in the current era of globalization needs to be considered because the Javanese language is a very large potential capable of encouraging the modernization process of society, especially those in rural areas. It cannot be denied that not all members of our society speak Indonesian. Therefore, during this decade the Javanese language is still relevant as a means of conveying various information to the public.

Becoming an advanced nation is an ideal that every country in the world wants to achieve. One of the factors that support the progress of a nation is education. Education is all learning activities that are planned, with organized material, carried out on a scheduled basis in a supervision system, and given

an evaluation based on predetermined goals (Suhartono, 2009). Education is one of the basic things that can be used as a basis for achieving success. So, including Javanese education in the world of education is one way to bridge success by maximizing local potential.

Based on the description above, a model, design or learning media is needed that is under the diversity of students. Unfortunately, there are many obstacles faced by teachers in learning Javanese. The main obstacles faced by Javanese language subject teachers include the lack of learning media, lack of student interest and motivation, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, and teacher administrative burdens. Since the introduction of Teacher Certification, teachers have become increasingly busy with administrative tasks as a result of becoming “professional teachers”. The focus and attention to students is increasingly fading, lesson plans are rarely modified, learning media and teaching aids are rarely found by students. As a result, students become bored quickly in learning (Aribowo, 2018).

From tracing the results of PTK that the researchers conducted on the [Garuda - Garba Rujukan Digital](#), not many new learning media have been produced and new learning models have become answers or solutions to problems. in learning Javanese. In the learning model, for example, most teachers are still struggling with the TPS, Jigsaw, STAD, Role Playing, and even lecturing learning models. Not many teachers have dared to explore learning models, especially new learning media from the results of years of teaching experience, so it can be said that the learning model applied to Javanese language subjects is less dynamic and saturating.

This fact is also possible due to the status of the Javanese as a subject that has not been tested in the National Final Examination or does not have a special tendency in requirements in the world of further education or the world of work, so that the enthusiasm to be creative, meaningful, learn less. Learning media is also another obstacle because teachers have difficulty finding Javanese learning media on the market (compared to Indonesian or foreign languages such as English or Arabic). In general posters, text books, and worksheets can only be found at local bookstores. Based on recent observations by researchers, some Javanese language magazines are increasingly exclusive by only serving orders based on a pre-order system.

Learning media is one of the main problems that teachers often complain about, even though the ideas of making learning media has been revealed several times, one of which is in the research conducted by (Kartikasari & Nugroho, 2010) entitled *Media Pembelajaran Interaktif Mata Pelajaran Bahasa Jawa Pokok Bahasan Aksara Jawa pada Sekolah Menengah Pertama Negeri 2 Tawanghari Kabupaten Sukoharjo*. Learning media is actually included in one of the main tasks of the teacher, namely designing meaningful learning for students so that they are motivated to increase knowledge, skills, and character.

Research on material enrichment in Javanese language learning has been carried out, but most of the forms are books that are likely only consumed by certain groups such as (Azizah, 2013) who developed contextual-based Javanese folklore reading books in Brebes Regency, (Nurhasanah,

Arif Budi Wuriyanto, 2014) which has developing KIJANK Media (*Komik Indonesia, Jawa, dan Aksara Jawa*) as Javanese language learning for 5th-grade elementary school students, (Suryanto, 2017) who have developed the aspirations of learning folklore using small puppet media, and (Thooyibah, 2017) who has developed the Grobogan folk tale book as an enrichment of folklore material in junior high schools.

The topic of developing web-based material enrichment was chosen because it is one of the potentials to solve common problems or obstacles faced by almost all schools. Another reason is that the website can be easily integrated into Javanese language learning materials because of its high level of flexibility. The reason for choosing Javanese language learning in vocational high schools is not only because of the position of researchers who are Javanese language teachers in vocational schools but psychologically middle and high school students also prefer experimental and exploration actions so they get bored quickly in learning, which applies a less dynamic learning model. Children at this age begin to enjoy learning something according to their needs and desires independently. With the development of this enrichment website, it is hoped that it can be a solution to all the challenges and problems faced by Javanese language teachers at the vocational school level in general.

Based on the discussions above, the researcher then took the research title "*Prototype Pre-Class Website Development As An Improvement of Java Language Learning in SMK*".

Literature Review

In the development of pre-class website enrichment, the researcher refers to the article *“The Principle of Beautiful Website Design (2nd Edition)”* by Jason Beard. There are two main points of view from some people in determining whether a website design is good or bad, namely from a usability point of view which focuses on function, effective presentation of information and efficiency, and an aesthetic point of view including presentation, animation, and good graphics. Thus, a website is said to be good if designers can combine the two points of view, not only from a usability point of view but also from an aesthetic side (Beard, 2010)

Furthermore, users will be happy with a website that includes content in its design. Developers can do this by designing a website based on layout and composition rules including web page anatomy, grid theory, balance, unity, emphasis, fresh trend, and resizing: fixed, fluid, or responsive layouts.

Web Page Anatomy

In designing a website some limitations cause several structural designs and rules to appear, such as headers, navigation, content area, and sidebar, footers, and sometimes backgrounds (Miller, 2011). Meanwhile, (Beard, 2010) concluded that although there are several blocks, sizes, and website titles, most websites have components, namely containers, logos, navigation, content, footers, and whitespace.

Balance and Unity

Balance is a state or similarity between opposing forces and creates a visually balanced impression. The concept of visual balance is a connecting element between equations that are physically depicted. If elements on the other side of a layout are the same size, then it is called balance with other elements (Beard, 2010). There are two kinds of visual balance, namely symmetrical balance, and asymmetrical balance. Symmetrical balance or formal balance occurs when a composition has the same elements as one side of the axis. Symmetrical balance is divided into two, namely; Bilateral symmetry occurs when a composition is balanced on more than one axis, radial symmetry is the symmetry that occurs when elements are equal from a central point. Asymmetrical balance or informal balance that includes differences in size, shape, color, content, position, texture, and eye direction.

Design theory describes Unity as how the various elements of a composition interact with one another. There are two approaches to achieve unity in a layout, namely: proximity and repetition (Beard, 2010). The proximity approach is grouping related items, bringing related items closer together, and grouping related items into one cohesive group. While the repetition approach is the repetition of several design aspects in all parts, it can also be called consistency (University, n.d.).

Emphasis and Fresh Trend

Emphasis (Emphasis) is about how to make certain features to attract user attention (Ostergren, 2008). Emphasis is intended to attract the attention of readers or people who see website design, the

emphasis is also known as COI (center of interest) (University, n.d.). This principle can be done by placement (continuity), isolation (isolation), contrast (contrast), proportion, and (proportion) (Beaird, 2007). On the website, this can be applied by making a raster or keynote box with a border, a fairly striking font size, and making contrasts in textures, colors, lines, spaces, and shapes or motifs.

In determining the layout and composition, you also pay attention to the styles that are trending. Some of the trends that are often used on websites are magazine-style without navigation, expansion footer, minimalism without bones.

Methodology

The subjects involved in this study were Javanese language teachers at SMK in Malang City. The research method used is the ADDIE development research method, following the model developed by (Branch, 2010) with research procedures including (1) Analysis; (2) Design; (3) Develop; (4) Implementation; and (5) Evaluation. Based on these steps, the research procedure is divided into three main stages.

In the first stage, a *needs analysis* is carried out by analyzing needs with the following objectives.

- Identifying the implementation of the Javanese language learning process in vocational schools throughout Malang Raya.
- Identifying facilities and infrastructure (media) used in the Javanese language teaching and learning process at SMK in Malang.
- Identification of currently used material enrichment models.

- Identification of the impact of applying the enrichment model used.

The second stage is the development of the results of the first stage of research, the steps are as follows.

- Develop a material enrichment website called a "Pre-class" website.
- Developed the "Pre-class" website operating system guide
- Validation of the two products mentioned above by involving *experts* such as Javanese learning experts, and design experts so that both products have content validity that can be justified.

The third stage is the stage of conducting trials (experiments) using the "pre-class" enrichment website for 30 students of class XII SMKN 3 Malang in the 2020/2021 school year. The data source in this research is primary data (obtained from the results of observations and interviews with Javanese language teachers throughout Malang Raya), while the data collection techniques used are through observation and interviews. The data collection instrument was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was used to reveal data about student responses to the pre-class website. The data obtained were analyzed descriptively quantitatively, to know the trend of each research variable.

Result and Discussion

Phase I Research

Description of research data and discussion of Phase I research can be explained below.

Implementation of Javanese Language Learning Process in Vocational High Schools in Malang City

In the Javanese learning process at SMK in Malang, Javanese language teachers have not provided optimal opportunities for students to be able to develop their creativity. This happens because of several things, including: (1) the teaching style of the Javanese language teacher who always asks students to memorize various concepts without being accompanied by an understanding of the concept (this is because most of the original Javanese language book teachers are graduates of the Javanese language education study program), (2) there are still many Javanese language teachers who consider teaching as an activity to explain concepts, (3) the proposed semester test questions and final exams in Javanese language learning only focus on cognitive aspects which are generally multiple-choice (there are even teachers who only copy and post questions from the internet to give to students); and (4) school facilities to support students in developing their creativity, especially those related to the development of the world of knowledge of Javanese language and culture which is generally inadequate.

Another thing that can be identified in the learning process of the Javanese language at SMK in Malang is that Javanese language teachers cannot arouse students' enthusiasm to ask questions, seek answers and construct every Javanese language problem faced through guesses (predictions), observation, experiment (conducting experiments) and interpretation.

Facilities (Media) Used in the Teaching and Learning Process of Javanese in Malang City

From the analysis of the needs of Javanese language teachers at SMK in Malang City, it can be said that the supporting facilities for student learning are still lacking in terms of enrichment of materials to increase student knowledge, through the unavailability of Javanese language books. From observations of the Javanese language learning process in the classroom, the teacher is also less creative because it rarely has learning media, so that the learning process that should use the media cannot be done by Javanese language teachers generally teach a lot by explaining theory. in the form of a lecture. For this media-free teaching method, it is understandable because the position of Javanese language learning is less profitable, most of the Javanese language teaching teachers move from one teacher to another every year. Javanese learning is widely used to cover the shortage of teaching hours for teachers in vocational schools throughout Malang.

The Impact of Implementation of Javanese Language Learning Process in Vocational High Schools in Malang City

As a result of the various learning strategies that are applied not under the type of learning and the character of vocational students in Javanese language learning will harm students in learning concepts in Javanese learning. Therefore, good and fun learning is learning that provides opportunities for students to convey ideas according to what they know. A learning process like this will change the paradigm in the Javanese language learning process from Teacher-Centered to Learner-Centered

Learning which is expected to encourage students to be actively involved in building knowledge, attitudes, and behavior. Through the learning process with the active involvement of students, it means that Javanese language teachers do not deprive students of their right to learn in a true sense. In the student-centered Javanese learning process, students get the opportunity and facilitation to build their knowledge, thereby gaining deep understanding (deep learning), and ultimately improving the quality of student learning outcomes. Therefore, students need to be provided with enrichment. - The amount of material enrichment so that in the future the student-centered learning process can be achieved immediately, the development of this website tries to overcome the shortcomings of material enrichment.

Research Phase II and III

Descriptions of research data and discussion of Phase II and III studies can be explained below.

Pre-Class Website Prototype

After knowing the needs of teachers and students for the enrichment of Javanese learning materials, the researcher then designed a pre-class website prototype. The pre-class website prototype is based on the formulated enrichment website development principles.

According to (Beaird, 2010), several principles must be considered in the website design process, including layout and composition, color, texture, typography, and images. There are two main points of view from some people in determining the merits of a website design, namely in terms of usability which focuses on function, presentation of information, and effective efficiency, and an

aesthetic point of view including presentation, animation and nice graphics. Thus, a website is said to be good if the designer can combine the two points of view, not only from the usability side but also from the aesthetic side. Usability is an important aspect of a website because if these aspects are not met, the website will be difficult to use and understand, and will not provide the information that users need. This can result in users not interested in re-accessing the website (Nielsen, 1994).

Based on the above opinion, this prototype is focused on a simple design but prioritizes user comfort. The researcher then divided the enrichment website into four main sections, namely: homepage, about me, enrichment, library, and contact section. The homepage contains an overview of the website content and the researchers' goals for developing the website.

The about me section contains a website developer resume containing a track record. A track record is a person's past journey that provides an overview or explanation of what has been done (Hermanto, Purwatiningsih, & Muhamad, 2020). A person's track record is very important to be displayed to convince readers in accessing website content, the better a person's past, whether in work, environment, business, in the family or community service, this will be a very important consideration for accessors website to make a good decision to keep accessing the website content or ignore it.

In the enrichment section, website developers don't forget to include illustrations, references, or reference sources for presentations. In this website, the developer strives for illustrations/images that suit the needs of teachers and students. Where the illustration according to

(B.P.Sitepu, 2005) is a sign/symbol that uses meaning in communicating, then the illustrations on this enrichment website are included in iconic symbols. The iconic symbol itself describes the actual object or situation, such as photography, painting, illustration. The use of images on this enrichment website is based on the needs of teachers and students. The existence of pictures in this book also serves to make a more concrete concept so that it arouses student interest and motivation and attracts students' attention in reading books. In addition, having pictures on the website will also help students remember the contents of the book for longer.

The digital library section contains material in the form of e-books which are divided into several groups, namely: (1) *koran, majalah, dan jurnal*, (2) *Komik*, (3) *Kisah, Cerita, dan Kronikal*, (4) *Arsip dan Sejarah*, (5) *Bahasa dan Budaya*, dan (6) *Agama dan Kepercayaan*. Developers deliberately label and divide them into several groups because according to (Saputra, 2015) labeling is a very important product element that needs to be considered carefully to attract consumers. By labeling and classifying books according to existing labels, the researchers hope that consumers, in this case, students, can more easily find the books they want to read according to their needs.

The last part of this enrichment website contacts, contacts can be used by website visitors to contact the developer if they feel they need help with a problem they are having. The developer also places several social media symbols such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn in several places such as at the bottom of the website, on the homepage to facilitate communication with the developer.

Figure 1.

Image of [Pre-Class Website](#) Prototype Display

Pre-Class Website Usage Management System as Enrichment Material

In the field of operational systems division, the researcher divides the operational system into 3 parts, namely for contributors who upload content from the pre-class website (for now research contributors are drawn from several cultural colleagues and observers of Javanese culture who are willing to renegotiate researchers.), Admin checks the enrichment website content control and tidying and managing the receipt of files and content on the enrichment website, participants who access the enrichment website content.

1) Working system for contributors

Contributors must first deposit a Gmail-based email account to the admin then the admin will add contributors to the system so that on the pre-class website application contributors can upload files at will, fill in articles as material enrichment content, and can download material on the system.

2) Work system for admin

Before carrying out activities on the system, the admin must log in first. After logging in, admins can add folders to Google Drive which are directly linked to the digital library page on the pre-class website, admins can also upload,

update, delete materials uploaded by contributors.

3) How the system works for participants

Participants can freely access the pre-class site, download materials, and share materials on the website without registering first. However, if participants wish to receive regular notifications, they must first register a Gmail-based email account via the member form on the pre-class website and or press the subscribe button on the pre-class page.

Validation Results from Experts

After the pre-class website prototype as enrichment for Javanese language learning in vocational high schools, the prototype was assessed by media expert lecturers and material expert lecturers.

Aspect of Media

According to media expert lecturers, the media developed on the pre-class website is good enough and can help students increase their knowledge before entering class. This website-based Javanese language enrichment media has advantages, among others, is media that is safe and easy to use, and is naturally flexible (easy to move downward). The media validation questionnaire after the researcher carried out the design received several suggestions or comments from media experts, namely: (a) determining the enrichment of the material to be tested on a limited trial, for example learning to write articles, texts containing Javanese customs, et al, (b) trying to study According to Mojok and Tirto. id, the blog writing style is because according to media experts a good writing style will further maximize the function of

the website. The validation results obtained from instructional media experts obtained a total score of 55 scores and showed a percentage of 84.6%. The percentage value of media validation that shows a range of 70% -84% means that the media developed is valid in terms of coloring (color), use of words or language (text layout), graphics, interface design, and layout.

Material Aspect

According to the material expert lecturer, the material developed on this enrichment website is good enough and can help students increase their knowledge and understanding of Javanese learning material. The material expert also considered that the website developed did not contain SARA. However, this material expert lecturer regretted that the language used on this website was only Indonesian. The material expert lecturer suggested that at least two languages, namely Indonesian and Javanese, be used to enrich student vocabulary. Based on the results of material expert validation, a total score of 47 was obtained with the remaining percentage being 94%. The quality of the material displayed is very good and worthy of being used as a medium to enrich learning.

Student Response to Pre-Class Website

To check student responses if this pre-class website will be developed as enrichment for Javanese learning material, the researchers decided to conduct a user assessment trial of 30 students of level XII for the 2020/2021 school year at SMKN 3 Malang. User trials were conducted using a questionnaire calculated based on the Likert scale method. The Likert scale is a measurement scale developed by Liker (1932). The Likert scale has four

or more question items that are combined to form a score/value that represents individual characteristics, such as knowledge, attitudes, and behavior. In the data analysis process, a combined score, usually the sum or average, of all question items can be used (Budiaji, 2013).

Each question in the user assessment has 5 answer choices, by giving a score for each answer, namely very good answer (SB) has a score of 5, good answer (B) has a score of 4, enough answer (C) has a score of 3, the answer is less (K) score 2 and very poor answer (SK) score 1. To determine the interval distance from the lowest 0% to the highest 100% the formula (2.1) $I = 100/5$ (number of answer choices) is used. So that the results obtained from a distance interval of 20. Thus the interpretation criteria based on the interval can be seen in table 1.

Table 1.
Assesment Interval

Percentage	Explanation	Initial
0%-19,9%	<i>Sangat Kurang</i>	SK
20%-39,9%	<i>Kurang</i>	K
40%-59,9%	<i>Cukup</i>	C
60%-79,9%	<i>Baik</i>	B
80%-100%	<i>Sangat Baik</i>	SB

This questionnaire consists of 10 questions about the appearance and work of the system. The questions used in the questionnaire sheet are as shown in table 2.

Table 2.
Question on the Questionnaire

No.	Question
1.	The application is easy to access and runs well
2.	Website easy to use
3.	Website content is easy to understand
4.	In terms of interface
5.	Data processing speed
6.	Data display speed
7.	Completeness of the material on the website
8.	Are you satisfied with using the website?
9.	Is the website worth using?
10.	Can the website help enrich material during the learning process?

Table 3 shows the percentage and average system test results that have been calculated using the Likert scale method, making it easier to read user test results. The results obtained from testing using a questionnaire and calculated using the Likert method are 81.57% obtained from looking for the average, namely the total percentage divided by the number of questions, it can be concluded that testing using a questionnaire is included in the "Very Good" criteria according to the assessment interval flow in table 2.

Table 3.
Website Testing Results

No	Assessment					Total Score	%
	SB	B	C	K	SK		
1.	8	18	4	0	0	120	80%
2.	6	20	4	0	0	116	77,3%
3.	9	16	5	0	0	124	82,6%
4.	10	19	1	0	0	129	86%
5.	1	16	13	0	0	127	84,6%
6.	4	18	8	0	0	116	77,3%
7.	6	20	4	0	0	122	81,3%
8.	8	21	1	0	0	127	84,6%
9.	1	16	13	0	0	108	72%
10.	4	22	12	0	0	120	80%
Total Percentage							318%
Average							80%

Conclusion

Based on the findings and analysis as discussed in the previous chapter, the results of this study can be concluded as follows.

- The learning system, the learning process in Javanese language learning at SMK is still not optimal due to the limited availability of material enrichment. Besides, most of the Javanese language teachers do not have a Javanese language education background so that material enrichment is very important for them.
- Based on the weaknesses in the strategy and learning process, as well as the media applied by Javanese language teachers, it is necessary to make efforts to implement an enrichment website as an alternative to minimize the weaknesses that exist in teaching Javanese language teachers at SMK.
- In general, it can be concluded that the enrichment website can be further developed as an alternative to solving the

problems experienced by Javanese language subject teachers at SMK in Malang City.

Based on the findings obtained, it is suggested that in the framework of further action the results of this study are as follows.

- In Javanese subjects, Javanese In Javanese subjects, Javanese language teachers must always carry out self-evaluation as a reflection of the teaching strategies applied, so that students as Javanese subjects can learn with enthusiasm.
- The website enrichment model needs to be developed as an alternative to developing enrichment materials that can help Javanese language teachers explain the material to students.
- Javanese learning in the school curriculum needs to be further developed in various models, media, learning methods, and approaches that can develop democratic and humanist learning.

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